

TRIGONOMETRIC GENERATED L_p DEGREE OF APPROXIMATION BY SMOOTH PICARD SINGULAR INTEGRAL OPERATORS

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ABSTRACT. In this article we continue the study of smooth Picard singular integral operators that started in [3], see there chapters 10-14. This time the foundation of our research is a trigonometric Taylor's formula. We establish the L_p convergence of our operators to the unit operator with rates via Jackson type inequalities engaging the first L_p modulus of continuity. Of interest here is a residual appearing term. Note that our operators are not positive.

1. INTRODUCTION

We are motivated by [2], [3] chapters 10-14, and [4], [5]. We use a trigonometric new Taylor formula from [4], see also [5]. Here we consider some very general operators, the smooth Picard singular integral operators over the real line and we study further their L_p , $p \geq 1$, convergence properties quantitatively. We establish related inequalities involving the first L_p , $p \geq 1$, modulus of continuity with respect to L_p , $p \geq 1$, norm. We provide detailed proofs.

2. RESULTS

By [4], [5], for $f \in C^2(\mathbb{R})$ and $a, x \in \mathbb{R}$, we have by the trigonometric Taylor formula

$$f(x) - f(a) = f'(a) \sin(x-a) + 2f''(a) \sin^2\left(\frac{x-a}{2}\right) + \int_a^x [(f''(t) + f(t)) - (f''(a) + f(a))] \sin(x-t) dt. \quad (1)$$

For $r \in \mathbb{N}$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, we set

$$\alpha_j := \begin{cases} (-1)^{r-j} \binom{r}{j} j^{-n}, & j = 1, \dots, r, \\ 1 - \sum_{j=1}^r (-1)^{r-j} \binom{r}{j} j^{-n}, & j = 0, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

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that is

$$\sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j = 1. \quad (3)$$

Here we consider both $f, f'' \in L_p(\mathbb{R}) \cap C(\mathbb{R})$, $1 \leq p < \infty$.

For $x \in \mathbb{R}$, $\xi > 0$ we consider the Lebesgue integrals, so called smooth Picard operators

$$P_{r,\xi}(f, x) = \frac{1}{2\xi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j f(x + jt) \right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt, \quad (4)$$

see [2]; $P_{r,\xi}$ are not in general positive operators, see [3].

We notice by

$$\frac{1}{2\xi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt = 1, \quad (5)$$

that

$$P_{r,\xi}(c, x) = c, \text{ where } c \text{ is a constant,} \quad (6)$$

and

$$P_{r,\xi}(f, x) - f(x) = \frac{1}{2\xi} \left(\sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (f(x + jt) - f(x)) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right). \quad (7)$$

Denote by

$$\omega_1(f, h)_p := \sup_{\substack{t \in \mathbb{R} \\ |t| \leq h}} \|f(x+t) - f(x)\|_{p,x}, \quad (8)$$

the first L_p modulus of smoothness of f , $1 \leq p < \infty$.

By (1) we get that

$$\begin{aligned} f(x + jt) - f(x) &= f'(x) \sin(jt) + 2f''(x) \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) + \\ &\int_x^{x+jt} [(f''(s) + f(s)) - (f''(x) + f(x))] \sin(x + jt - s) ds, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

or better,

$$\begin{aligned} f(x + jt) - f(x) &= f'(x) \sin(jt) + 2f''(x) \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) + \\ &\int_0^{jt} [(f''(x+z) + f(x+z)) - (f''(x) + f(x))] \sin(jt - z) dz. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j [f(x + jt) - f(x)] &= \\ f'(x) \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \sin(jt) + 2f''(x) \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) + \\ \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \int_0^{jt} [(f''(x+z) + f(x+z)) - (f''(x) + f(x))] \sin(jt - z) dz, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

or better

$$\sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j [f(x + jt) - f(x)] =$$

$$f'(x) \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \sin(jt) + 2f''(x) \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) + \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j j \int_0^t [(f''(x+jw) + f(x+jw)) - (f''(x) + f(x))] \sin j(t-w) dw. \quad (12)$$

Call

$$R := R(t) :=$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j j \int_0^t [(f''(x+jw) + f(x+jw)) - (f''(x) + f(x))] \sin j(t-w) dw, \quad (13)$$

$\forall t \in \mathbb{R}$.

We notice that

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(x) &:= P_{r,\xi}(f, x) - f(x) - f'(x) \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \frac{1}{2\xi} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sin(jt) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) \\ &\quad - 2f''(x) \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \frac{1}{2\xi} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2\xi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R(t) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Next we simplify (14).

We observe that

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sin(jt) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt = \int_{-\infty}^0 \sin(jt) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt + \int_0^{\infty} \sin(jt) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt. \quad (15)$$

Notice $-\infty \leq t \leq 0 \Rightarrow \infty \geq -t \geq 0$. So that

$$-\int_{-\infty}^0 \sin(j(-(-t))) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} d(-t) = -\int_{-\infty}^0 (-\sin(j(-t))) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} d(-t) = \quad (16)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^0 (\sin j(-t)) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} d(-t) = \int_{\infty}^0 \sin j(t) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt = -\int_0^{\infty} \sin(jt) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt.$$

Therefore, it is

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sin(jt) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt = 0, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, r. \quad (17)$$

Furthermore, we have that

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt = 2 \int_0^{\infty} \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{t}{\xi}} dt, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, r. \quad (18)$$

The last follows by

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^0 \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt &= -\int_{-\infty}^0 \left(-\sin\left(\frac{j(-t)}{2}\right) \right)^2 e^{-\frac{|-t|}{\xi}} d(-t) \stackrel{(z=-t)}{=} \\ &= -\int_{\infty}^0 \sin^2\left(\frac{jz}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{|z|}{\xi}} dz = \int_0^{\infty} \sin^2\left(\frac{jz}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{z}{\xi}} dz. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Next, we calculate

$$\int_0^{\infty} \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{t}{\xi}} dt = \xi \int_0^{\infty} \sin^2\left(\left(\frac{j\xi}{2}\right) \frac{t}{\xi}\right) e^{-\frac{t}{\xi}} d\frac{t}{\xi} =$$

(call $\frac{t}{\xi} =: x$ and $\frac{j\xi}{2} =: a$)

$$\xi \int_0^\infty \sin^2(ax) e^{-x} dx = \quad (20)$$

(by Wolfram Alpha Computational Intelligence)

$$\xi \left(\frac{2a^2}{4a^2 + 1} \right) = \frac{j^2 \xi^3}{2(j^2 \xi^2 + 1)}.$$

Thus, we find that

$$\int_{-\infty}^\infty \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt = \frac{j^2 \xi^3}{j^2 \xi^2 + 1}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, r. \quad (21)$$

Consequently, it holds ($\xi > 0$)

$$\frac{1}{2\xi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt = \frac{j^2 \xi^2}{2(j^2 \xi^2 + 1)} \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } \xi \rightarrow 0, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, r. \quad (22)$$

Eventually we obtain

$$-2f''(x) \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \frac{1}{2\xi} \left(\int_{-\infty}^\infty \sin^2\left(\frac{jt}{2}\right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) = -f''(x) \left(\sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \frac{j^2}{(j^2 \xi^2 + 1)} \right) \xi^2. \quad (23)$$

Consequently, based on the above, it is

$$\Delta(x) = P_{r,\xi}(f, x) - f(x) - f''(x) \left(\sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \frac{j^2}{(j^2 \xi^2 + 1)} \right) \xi^2, \quad \xi > 0. \quad (24)$$

We present our first result, L_p approximation, $p > 1$.

Theorem 2.1. Let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, $\xi > 0$, and both $f, f'' \in L_p(\mathbb{R}) \cap C(\mathbb{R})$, $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Delta(x)\|_p &= \left\| P_{r,\xi}(f) - f - f'' \left(\sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_j \frac{j^2}{(j^2 \xi^2 + 1)} \right) \xi^2 \right\|_p \leq \\ &\quad \left(\frac{4(r+1)}{q(q+1)} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{2}{p} \right)^{2+\frac{1}{p}} \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_p \xi^2 \\ &\quad \left\{ \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left[\Gamma(qp - q + p + 1) + \frac{(2j)^p}{p^p (p+1)} \Gamma(qp - q + 2p + 1) \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{p}} \rightarrow 0, \quad (25) \end{aligned}$$

as $\xi \rightarrow 0$.

Above Γ stands for the gamma function.

Proof. Let

$$I := \int_0^t [(f''(x+jw) + f(x+jw)) - (f''(x) + f(x))] \sin j(t-w) dw, \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (26)$$

For $t < 0$, we have that

$$|I| = \left| \int_t^0 [(f''(x+jw) + f(x+jw)) - (f''(x) + f(x))] \sin j(t-w) dw \right| \leq$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_t^0 |(f''(x+jw) + f(x+jw)) - (f''(x) + f(x))| |\sin j(t-w)| dw \leq \quad (27) \\
& j \int_t^0 |(f''(x+jw) + f(x+jw)) - (f''(x) + f(x))| (w-t) dw = \\
& -j \int_t^0 |(f''(x-j(-w)) + f(x-j(-w))) - (f''(x) + f(x))| (-t - (-w)) d(-w) \\
& (t \leq w \leq 0 \Rightarrow -t \geq -w =: \theta \geq 0) \\
& = -j \int_{-t}^0 |(f''(x-j\theta) + f(x-j\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))| (-t - \theta) d\theta = \\
& j \int_0^{-t} |(f''(x-j\theta) + f(x-j\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))| (-t - \theta) d\theta = \quad (28) \\
& j \int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + \text{sign}(t)j\theta) + f(x + \text{sign}(t)j\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))| (|t| - \theta) d\theta.
\end{aligned}$$

So, we have proved that

$$|I| \leq j \int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + \text{sign}(t)j\theta) + f(x + \text{sign}(t)j\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))| (|t| - \theta) d\theta, \quad (29)$$

$\forall t \in \mathbb{R}$,

and by (13),

$$|R(t)| \leq \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2$$

$$\int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j\text{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j\text{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))| (|t| - \theta) d\theta, \quad (30)$$

$\forall t \in \mathbb{R}$.

By (14) we have

$$\Delta(x) = \frac{1}{2\xi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R(t) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt. \quad (31)$$

Hence it holds ($p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$),

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\Delta(x)|^p dx &= \frac{1}{(2\xi)^p} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R(t) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right|^p dx \leq \\
& \frac{1}{(2\xi)^p} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |R(t)| e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right)^p dx = \quad (32) \\
& \frac{1}{(2\xi)^p} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |R(t)| e^{-\frac{|t|}{2\xi}} e^{-\frac{|t|}{2\xi}} dt \right)^p dx \leq \\
& \frac{1}{(2\xi)^p} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |R(t)|^p e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right) \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{|qt|}{2\xi}} dt \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} dx = \\
& \frac{1}{(2\xi)^p} \left(\frac{4\xi}{q} \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |R(t)|^p e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right) dx = \\
& \frac{2^{p-2}\xi^{-1}}{q^{p-1}} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |R(t)|^p e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right) dx \right) =: (*).
\end{aligned}$$

But, we need to treat

$$|R(t)| \leq \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \quad (33)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))|^p d\theta \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \left(\int_0^{|t|} (|t| - \theta)^q d\theta \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} = \\ & \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))|^p d\theta \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \frac{|t|^{q+\frac{1}{q}}}{(q+1)^{\frac{1}{q}}} = \\ & \left\{ \sum_{j=0}^r (|\alpha_j| j^2)^p \right\}^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \left. \left(\int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))|^p d\theta \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right\} \\ & \frac{|t|^{q+\frac{1}{q}}}{(q+1)^{\frac{1}{q}}} \leq \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

$$(0 < \frac{1}{p} < 1)$$

$$\left\{ (r+1)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right.$$

$$\left. \left(\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))|^p d\theta \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right\}$$

$$\frac{|t|^{q+\frac{1}{q}}}{(q+1)^{\frac{1}{q}}}.$$

Hence, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} |R(t)|^p & \leq \left(\frac{r+1}{q+1} \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \right. \\ & \left. \left(\int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))|^p d\theta \right)^{\frac{(q+1)p}{q}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Therefore, we get

$$(*) \leq \left(\frac{2^{p-2}\xi^{-1}}{q^{p-1}} \left(\frac{r+1}{q+1} \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \right) \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\int_0^{|t|} \left[|(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))|^p d\theta \right] \\ \left. |t|^{\frac{(q+1)p}{q}} e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right\} dx \quad (36)$$

$$(\text{set } c_1 = \frac{2^{p-2}\xi^{-1}}{q^{p-1}} \left(\frac{r+1}{q+1}\right)^{\frac{2}{q}})$$

$$= c_1 \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))|^p d\theta \right] dx \right) \right. \\ \left. |t|^{\frac{(q+1)p}{q}} e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right\} \\ = c_1 \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \right. \right. \quad (37)$$

$$\left. \left. \int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - (f''(x) + f(x))|^p dx \right] d\theta \right\} \\ \left. |t|^{\frac{(q+1)p}{q}} e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right\} \leq$$

($\xi > 0$)

$$c_1 \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left(\int_0^{|t|} \omega_1 \left(f'' + f, \xi \frac{j\theta}{\xi} \right)_p^p d\theta \right) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. |t|^{\frac{(q+1)p}{q}} e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right\} \leq$$

$$\omega_1 \left(f'' + f, \xi \right)_p^p c_1 \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left(\int_0^{|t|} \left(1 + \frac{j}{\xi} \theta \right)^p d\theta \right) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. |t|^{(q+1)(p-1)} e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right\} \leq \quad (38)$$

$$c_1 \omega_1 \left(f'' + f, \xi \right)_p^p \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} 2^{p-1} \left(\int_0^{|t|} \left(1 + \frac{j^p}{\xi^p} \theta^p \right) d\theta \right) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. |t|^{(q+1)(p-1)} e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right\} =$$

$$2^{p-1} c_1 \omega_1 \left(f'' + f, \xi \right)_p^p \\ \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left(|t| + \frac{j^p |t|^{p+1}}{\xi^p p + 1} \right) |t|^{(q+1)(p-1)} e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right] \right\} =$$

$$2^{p-1} c_1 \omega_1 \left(f'' + f, \xi \right)_p^p \\ \left\{ \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(|t| + \frac{j^p |t|^{p+1}}{\xi^p p + 1} \right) |t|^{(q+1)(p-1)} e^{-\frac{|pt|}{2\xi}} dt \right\} = \quad (39) \\ 2^p c_1 \omega_1 \left(f'' + f, \xi \right)_p^p$$

$$\left\{ \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \int_0^\infty \left(t + \frac{j^p}{\xi^p (p+1)} t^{p+1} \right) t^{(q+1)(p-1)} e^{-\frac{pt}{2\xi}} dt \right\} =$$

$$2^p c_1 \omega_1 (f'' + f, \xi)_p^p$$

$$\left\{ \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left[\int_0^\infty t^{(q+1)(p-1)+1} e^{-\frac{pt}{2\xi}} dt + \frac{j^p}{\xi^p (p+1)} \int_0^\infty t^{(q+1)(p-1)+p+1} e^{-\frac{pt}{2\xi}} dt \right] \right\} =$$
(40)

$$2^p c_1 \omega_1 (f'' + f, \xi)_p^p \left\{ \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left[\xi^{qp-q+p+1} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{t}{\xi} \right)^{(q+1)(p-1)+1} e^{-(\frac{p}{2}) \frac{t}{\xi}} d \frac{t}{\xi} \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. + \frac{j^p}{\xi^p (p+1)} \xi^{qp-q+2p+1} \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{t}{\xi} \right)^{qp-q+2p} e^{-(\frac{p}{2}) \frac{t}{\xi}} d \frac{t}{\xi} \right] \right\} =$$

(above it is $(q+1)(p-1)+1 = qp-q+p > 0$, $(q+1)(p-1)+p+1 = qp-q+2p > 0$)

$$2^p c_1 \omega_1 (f'' + f, \xi)_p^p \xi^{qp-q+p+1} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left\{ \int_0^\infty x^{qp-q+p} e^{-(\frac{p}{2})x} dx \right. \right.$$
(41)

$$\left. \left. + \frac{j^p}{(p+1)} \int_0^\infty x^{qp-q+2p} e^{-(\frac{p}{2})x} dx \right\} \right] =$$

(next we use, for $a, b > 0$ that it holds $\int_0^\infty x^a e^{-bx} dx = b^{-a-1} \Gamma(a+1)$, by Wolfram Alpha computational intelligence)

$$2^p c_1 \omega_1 (f'' + f, \xi)_p^p \xi^{qp-q+p+1} \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left\{ \left(\frac{p}{2} \right)^{-qp+q-p-1} \Gamma(qp-q+p+1) \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. + \frac{j^p}{(p+1)} \left(\frac{p}{2} \right)^{-qp+q-2p-1} \Gamma(qp-q+2p+1) \right\} \right] =$$

$$\frac{2^{2(p-1)}}{q^{p-1}} \left(\frac{r+1}{q+1} \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \omega_1 (f'' + f, \xi)_p^p \xi^{qp-q+p} \quad (42)$$

$$\left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left\{ \left(\frac{p}{2} \right)^{-qp+q-p-1} \left(\Gamma(qp-q+p+1) + \frac{j^p}{(p+1)} \left(\frac{p}{2} \right)^{-p} \Gamma(qp-q+2p+1) \right) \right\} \right].$$

So for $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1, \xi > 0$, we have proved:

$$\int_{-\infty}^\infty |\Delta(x)|^p dx \leq \frac{2^{2(p-1)}}{q^{p-1}} \left(\frac{r+1}{q+1} \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \omega_1 (f'' + f, \xi)_p^p \xi^{qp-q+p} \left(\frac{p}{2} \right)^{-qp+q-p-1} \quad (43)$$

$$\left\{ \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left[\Gamma(qp-q+p+1) + \frac{(2j)^p}{p^p (p+1)} \Gamma(qp-q+2p+1) \right] \right\}.$$

The proof of the theorem is now completed. $\square$

Next comes the L_1 related approximation.

Theorem 2.2. Let $\xi > 0$, both $f, f'' \in L_1(\mathbb{R}) \cap C(\mathbb{R})$, $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Then

$$\|\Delta(x)\|_1 \leq \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 (2+3j) \right] \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1 \xi^2 \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } \xi \rightarrow 0. \quad (44)$$

Proof. We have that

$$\begin{aligned} |\Delta(x)| &= \frac{1}{2\xi} \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R(t) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right| \leq \frac{1}{2\xi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |R(t)| e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \leq \\ &\frac{1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - \right. \\ &\quad \left. (f''(x) + f(x))| (|t| - \theta) d\theta \right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

Thus, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Delta(x)\|_1 &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\Delta(x)| dx \leq \\ &\frac{1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - \right. \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left. (f''(x) + f(x))| (|t| - \theta) d\theta \right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) dx \right) \leq \\ &\frac{1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(|t| \int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - \right. \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left. (f''(x) + f(x))| d\theta \right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) dx \right) = \\ &\frac{1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(|t| \int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - \right. \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left. (f''(x) + f(x))| d\theta \right) e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dx \right) dt \right) = \\ &\frac{1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_0^{|t|} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - \right. \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left. (f''(x) + f(x))| d\theta \right) dx \right) |t| e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) = \\ &\frac{1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_0^{|t|} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |(f''(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta) + f(x + j \operatorname{sign}(t)\theta)) - \right. \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \left. (f''(x) + f(x))| dx \right) d\theta \right) |t| e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) \leq \\ &\frac{1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_0^{|t|} \omega_1(f'' + f, j\theta)_1 d\theta \right) |t| e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) \leq \\ &\frac{\omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_0^{|t|} \left(1 + \frac{j}{\xi} \theta \right) d\theta \right) |t| e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) = \\ &\frac{\omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1}{2\xi} \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[|t| + \frac{j}{\xi} \frac{|t|^2}{2} \right] |t| e^{-\frac{|t|}{\xi}} dt \right) = \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \xi^2 \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1 \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left(\int_0^\infty \left[\frac{t}{\xi} + \frac{j}{2} \left(\frac{t}{\xi} \right)^2 \right] \frac{t}{\xi} e^{-\frac{t}{\xi}} d\frac{t}{\xi} \right) = \\
& \xi^2 \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1 \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left[\int_0^\infty \left(t + \frac{j}{2} t^2 \right) t e^{-t} dt \right] = \\
& \xi^2 \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1 \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left[\int_0^\infty t^2 e^{-t} dt + \frac{j}{2} \int_0^\infty t^3 e^{-t} dt \right] = \\
& \xi^2 \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1 \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 \left[2 + \frac{j}{2} \cdot 6 \right] = \\
& \xi^2 \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1 \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 [2 + 3j]. \tag{49}
\end{aligned}$$

Above we used that

$$\int_0^\infty t^2 e^{-t} dt = 2 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^\infty t^3 e^{-t} dt = 6.$$

The theorem is proved. $\square$

We finish with the following

Corollary 2.3. (to Theorem 2.1) It holds

$$\begin{aligned}
\|P_{r,\xi}(f) - f\|_p & \leq \|f''\|_p \left(\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| \frac{j^2}{(j^2 \xi^2 + 1)} \right) \xi^2 + \\
& \left(\frac{4(r+1)}{q(q+1)} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{2}{p} \right)^{2+\frac{1}{p}} \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_p \xi^2 \tag{50}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\left\{ \sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j|^p j^{2p} \left[\Gamma(qp - q + p + 1) + \frac{(2j)^p}{p^p(p+1)} \Gamma(qp - q + 2p + 1) \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{p}} \rightarrow 0,$$

as $\xi \rightarrow 0$.

Corollary 2.4. (to Theorem 2.2) It holds

$$\begin{aligned}
\|P_{r,\xi}(f) - f\|_1 & \leq \|f''\|_1 \left(\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| \frac{j^2}{(j^2 \xi^2 + 1)} \right) \xi^2 + \\
& \left[\sum_{j=0}^r |\alpha_j| j^2 (2 + 3j) \right] \omega_1(f'' + f, \xi)_1 \xi^2 \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{as } \xi \rightarrow 0. \tag{51}
\end{aligned}$$

Conclusion: A new type of approximation was introduced for singular integrals. The interesting trigonometric based one.

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